

Challenges and Classroom Practices of Teachers Towards the Development of School-Wide Support System for Inclusive Education

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Abstract

Regular teachers or receiving teachers are face various challenges in handling learners with special needs in a regular classroom. The aim of this study is to determine the practices and challenges of the teachers in handling learners with special needs in a regular classroom in selected schools in Cavite. To best serve the answers to the research questions and the goals of the study, this study used mixed method. A localized questionnaire was utilized to gather data and conducted an interview about the practices and challenges of regular teachers in selected Elementary Schools in Bacoor City, Cavite. The study utilized descriptive statistics and inferential statistics to determine the accurate data. Based on the findings it was revealed that the level of knowledge, skills, training, and practice of receiving teachers are in average. Then, the level of support they received are in average also. In

the result of interviewed, it was revealed that the challenges of teachers are frustrations in classroom, classroom management, effects in methods of teaching, classroom practices and lack of training. They also lack support from the administration and stakeholders. It was also found out that not all teachers in selected elementary schools in Cavite who handles inclusive education are trained in special needs education. This present study thereby recommends having an annual, quarterly, or series of trainings to continuously provide the trainings and to impart more knowledge to receiving teachers. It also their way to address their challenges, concern, and problems. Continuous support and collaboration were needed and recommended to maintain the implementation of Inclusive Education.

Keywords: *Receiving teachers, learners with special needs, Inclusive education, practices, challenges*

1. Introduction

This study comes from the fact that very little is known about the practice of educational inclusion in the Philippines. The absence of a shared approach to education in the country, one that is open to all children, suggests that a strong conceptual basis for inclusive education (IE) continues to be created. This study comes from the fact that very little is known about the practice of educational inclusion in the Philippines.

The absence of a shared approach to education in the country, one that is open to all children, suggests that a strong conceptual basis for inclusive education (IE) continues to be created. This study's main objective is to evaluate the situation and problems receiving teachers encounter when working in inclusion settings with learners who have special needs. The researcher is interested in learning more about the difficulties faced by receiving teachers in Bacoor City, Cavite, as a special education teacher in a public school. In a self-contained classroom or a regular classroom, where the subjects, lessons, and curriculum are based on the grade level of regular learners and should be adjusted as needed, the receiving teachers will work with the students who have special needs. It was also mentioned that there was a growing confusion between the responsibilities of regular teachers and special education teachers from the article by O'Leary (2019).

1.1 Research Objectives

Specifically, the research answers the following problems:

- What is the level of knowledge, skills, training, and seminar possessed by receiving teachers in handling learners with special education needs?
- What is the level of support they received and the challenges that the receiving teachers experience with Learners with Disabilities (LWD)?
- Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Awareness, Knowledge, and Skills of Receiving Teachers and Level of Collaboration and Support for Receiving Teachers?
- How do these challenges affect your methods in teaching Learners with Disabilities (LWD)?
- Hypothesis:
- Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Awareness, Knowledge, and Skills of Receiving Teachers and Level of Collaboration and Support for Receiving Teachers?

2. Methods

2.1 Research Design

This study is a mixed-methods research that captures all aspects of the human experience more effectively than qualitative or quantitative research. (Aramide, 2023). The researcher can increase understanding of topics.

2.2 Participants

The respondents of this research are thirty (30) Receiving Teachers in a regular classroom handling learners with special needs in different grade levels in public school in the City of Bacoor, Cavite

2.3 Data Collection Instruments

A localized self constructed questionnaire for both quantitative and qualitative

Inferential statistics one of the most reliable ways for predicting how a collection of data will scale when applied to a larger group of participants.

Mean. It was a measure of central tendency and computed by summing all scores and dividing by the number of subjects

Standard deviation measures the degree of data variability. It represents the deviation of each observed value from the mean.

Descriptive statistics to present data exactly as it is provided. Thus, the data should not be presented with any assumptions or generalizations.

2.4 Procedure

Surveys were distributed online via Google Forms. Teacher interviews were conducted via Zoom and recorded with consent.

2.5 Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Interview responses were transcribed and analyzed thematically using QUADAS.

3. Results

3.1 Quantitative Findings

In research number 1 shows that across 15 items, 14 were interpreted as Average, indicating that the level of knowledge of the 30 respondents were on Practical Application.

In research number 2 shows that there have been varying levels of Collaboration and Support for Receiving Teachers that have been evident based on the results of the analysis of data.

In research number 3 at 90% level of confidence, there has been a reported statistically significant relationship between the Level of Awareness, Knowledge, and Skills of Receiving Teachers and Level of Collaboration and Support for Receiving Teachers. This indicates that as the Level of Awareness and Knowledge of the Receiving teachers approaches Recognized Authority, they are also likely to be on the Collaboration level when it comes to Level of Collaboration and Support for Receiving Teachers.

There is no generally applicable definition or approach to execution for all individuals and situations. The approach prioritizes inclusive and adaptable techniques for various scenarios. When faced with a variety of uncommon incidents and levels of severity, regular teachers explain teaching strategies and methods tailored to each LSEN's specific needs. Creating group activities, hands-on learning, and utilizing the LSEN's socialization abilities has been effective for teachers. Respondents share their experiences on the challenges they had in the regular classroom handling LSENs.

3.2 Qualitative Findings

Three main themes emerged from teacher interviews:

Classroom Management Based on the responses of the teachers they all agreed in describing the challenging part in handling learners with LWD is implementing classroom management.

Effects in Methods of Teaching Based in the responses of the teachers they all agreed in describing the challenging part in handling learners with LWD is implementing classroom management.

Classroom Practices Based on the responses of the teachers they all gave the classroom practices they are utilizing to handle the LWDs.

Lack of training Based on the responses teachers agreed that they need proper training in handling LSENs. T1 said that she received support from SNED teachers, LGU, and stakeholders.

4. Discussion

The findings suggest to address the challenges that teachers encounter in Inclusive Education and handling learners with special needs, the researchers recommend the following that supports from school administrations and stakeholders should be given more focus on supporting and giving training to regular teachers.

5.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Most of them are adjusting their strategies in teaching and learning to be suitable for learners with disabilities. Given the amount of evidence in the literature indicating that general education teachers lack comprehensive knowledge about how to engage with children with special needs in the classroom, these findings may come as no surprise (Bruggnick et al., 2015). They also mentioned that when students start to misbehave like tantrums, teachers have trouble in handling them. Given that teachers are regarded as vital to attaining the goal of inclusive education, this appears unusual. Because they are viewed as the basis for integrating LSENs into regular class, they were critical to the effective implementation of inclusive education.

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